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Current threats in TB prevention: suggestions for Italy

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Abstract

As for other countries, tuberculosis (TB) prevention has a long history in Italy. Nevertheless, despite successful past prevention policies, it seems to be difficult to decisively eradicate TB at the moment and, furthermore, the country is at high-risk for the recrudescence of the disease due to multi and extensively-drug resistant TB cases and for many other concurrent factors.

This short communication provides a brief overview about some of the recent and potential threats (Covid-19, healthcare workers, migrations, mental health diseases) to face in order to improve the TB prevention programmes in Italy.

Key words:

Tuberculosis; TB; Italy, Prevention; Occupational health.

Text:

In Italy, starting from the second half of the Eighteenth Century, the first concrete results against the so-called “consumption”, “phthisis” or “ulceration of the lung” were achieved thanks to specific territorial laws (as the “preventive laws of the Kingdom of Naples” - on the 19th of July, 1782 – issued in the Southern area of the peninsula).[1]

Gradually, measures of tuberculosis (TB) prevention increased in appropriateness during decades. The Piedmontese physician Biagio Castaldi reported the positive effects of high altitudes, balanced diet, rest, and elementary norms of hygiene in patients affected by TB.

In the country following the experience from the first sanatorium founded in Germany in 1854, the awareness about some risk factors for TB transmission and about common relieving treatments increased thanks to the activities of mountains’ sanatoria in the Northern and in the Centre of Italy and thanks to the first local committees against tuberculosis (in Siena, Pisa, and Padua).

Between the end of the 1800s and the beginning of the 1900s there was an improvement on diagnostic and recovery perspectives due to: the experience of doctor Edoardo Maragliano in Genoa, the built of the first specialised hospitals (e.g., in Budrio and, for working-class people, in Valtellina), and the arrangement of the first Italian Congress against TB held in Milan (1906).[2]

Meanwhile, the physician and microbiologist Robert Koch discovered the tubercle bacilli as the causative agents of tuberculosis on the 24th March 1882.[3]

Thenceforth, the awareness about the airborne transmission of TB, the epidemic of the disease (especially among poorest people), and the experiences from the field supported many researchers to highlight on the importance of reaching the majority of the achievable population with preventive measures and basic hygiene levels (e.g. water and food supply, room ventilation, active patients isolation, avoid raw milk and dairy products from cows affected by bovine tuberculosis, etc.).[4,5]

By the middle of the Twentieth Century these prevention policies dramatically reduced the incidence of TB cases in the Western countries even before the introduction of the antibiotic treatment against TB bacilli.

Unfortunately, nowadays tuberculosis is still a great global public health emergency: there are 10 millions of new infections Worldwide;[6] deaths from TB are estimated to be 1.5 million;[7] the amount of people with latent tuberculosis infection (LTBI) is about one-fourth of the global population.[8] In 2020 data from Italy reported an incidence rate of 6.6 TB cases per 100,000

population; the TB case fatality ratio in the same year was about 9%. [9]

Some topics about open possibilities in the TB prevention are still remarkable. Some examples are shown below:

1) TB and Covid-19

Covid-19 pandemic suddenly stressed about the importance of public health structured responses. These pre-programmed and coordinated activities are also largely requested for an “old” and “less feeding frenzy” disease like tuberculosis.

So, the improvement of measures to avoid airborne transmission and to enhance contact tracing and the public health investments can also be applied for the TB contention. [10,11]

2) TB and healthcare workers

As is known the incidence of TB cases among healthcare workers (HCWs) is lower in countries with low incidence rates and low prevalence among general population (e.g., in Italy) and it is higher in countries with high TB incidence rates and prevalence (e.g., Thailand, Taiwan). [12]

Noteworthy, the extensive use of tuberculin skin test (TST) or interferon-gamma releasing assay (IGRA) in the occupational surveillance programmes and the implementation of safety measures during the care of potentially affected TB-active patients in the health settings are related with lower TB incidence rates among HCWs. [13] Making a culture of prevention increases health professionals' compliance and it represents a key factor against TB among HCWs and, at the same time, among general population globally.

3) TB and migrants

Migrations are even more very common phenomena; they are related to a wide range of different factors (e.g., conflicts, climate changes, water supply, communicable diseases, economic conditions, geographical proximity, etc.).

Migratory flows are usually directed from low-middle income countries (LMIC) to high-income countries (HIC). Generally, the LMIC also present a higher-incidence TB rate (more than 10 cases for 100,000 population) [14] and a higher-prevalence of LTBI cases. [8]

It is well-known that good and successful immigration policies are strictly related with public health prevention programmes. Despite these well-known assumptions it seems that the screening campaigns for LTBI and active TB infections and the improvement of the related preventive treatments and curative plans for migrants are still far from being adopted in many migrants-receiving countries. [14]

4) TB and Mental Health

Mental illness is a risk factor for developing active TB. So, co-existence of mental health conditions and tuberculosis is highly possible and it is necessary to reach this population group with targeted interventions for TB screening and integrated treatments. [15]

In the light of the global increase of mental health problems for the Covid-19 direct (e.g., infection delayed effects) and the indirect (e.g., prolonged “lock-down” isolation, mental health services disruption, income loss and unemployment, etc.) effects it is necessary to plan prevention programmes in order to actively research and treat mental health conditions and, at the same time, identify high-risk groups for LTBI and active TB. [16]

So, despite the millennial history of cohabitation with humans, tuberculosis remains a big global public health emergency; the updating ability of this disease it is also related with the recent multi-drug and extensively-drug resistant abilities of TB bacteria. [7]

In the light of these well-known peculiarities of the disease and considering the reported topics it is necessary to provide an adequate update of the Italian TB health prevention policies urgently.

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